

APP

Catalog for sustainability principles & action points

Sources can be viewed via QR code:

Guiding principles for sustainability

Guiding principles of sustainability are principles of action and behaviour for guiding product design to integrate sustainability into a product.

The guiding principles and their action points were developed from the sources mentioned in the footnote.¹ The action points show which activities can be implemented in terms of sustainable product design.

Reusability

The term reuse indicates that already existing resources are used to create something new². In terms of the sustainability of IT (software & hardware), this can be applied to the reuse of software, libraries or components as well as the longest possible and most efficient use of hardware and software. Possible action points for the guiding principle of reusability are listed below:

- Independence: decoupling of functionalities from hardware
- Regular updates and reuse of codes: use of coding libraries, frameworks and low-code tools
- Use of software development tool kits
- Update capability
- Operation of data centers:
 - Use of process water for data centers
 - Conversion of data centers so that treated water can be used
 - Use of renewable energies
 - Prolonged use of hardware
 - Recycling strategy for hardware
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Avoiding negative effects:

The production or consumption of certain goods as well as the provision and receipt of services can result in disadvantages (negative effects) for third parties. These effects have a negative impact on people and the environment but are not factored into the prices and profits of the producing or service-providing companies³. In terms of sustainability of IT (software & hardware), the aim is to avoid possible negative effects, such as the consumption of water for data centers instead of for agriculture⁴. Other negative effects are the need to handle toxic substances, conflicts due to rare earths⁵ and planned obsolescence⁶ (practice of designing products to break quickly or become obsolete in the short to mid-term⁷). Possible action points for avoiding or reversing the negative effects of IT are listed below:

¹ see Environment | Ethical consumer, 2023; Sustainability - Positive Marks | Ethical consumer, 2021; Hilty et al, 2017; Jardim, 2017; TCO Certification, 2023.

² cf. Stütze, 2002, p.11.

³ See Waschbusch, 2018.

⁴ cf. Benoit, 2023.

⁵ cf. deutschlandfunk.de, undated.

⁶ cf. Dallmus, 2022.

⁷ see iberdrola 2024.

- **Avoiding "green-washing"**: Do not make false environmental promises.
- **Proactive climate policy**: Realistic targets and transparent reporting
- **Avoidance of addiction among users**, e.g. through ethical design principles, time recording of activity, etc.
- **Transparency about negative effects**: Reporting on negative effects of the product
- **Reducing land use for data centers**: Data centers should be built in an efficient way and consume little land.
- **Anti-corruption measures**: Defining clear processes to prevent corruption

Conservation of resources

Conservation of resources refers to the efficient use of natural resources in order to minimize their consumption and preserve their availability for present and future generations. This approach aims to reduce environmental impact, avoid waste and promote sustainable production and consumption habits. Conservation of resources is based on the principle that natural resources are limited and should be used responsibly to minimize environmental impacts and maintain ecological balances⁸. Possible action points for this guiding principle are listed below:

- Introduction of an **energy-saving** mode as standard for hardware and software, e.g. by automatically activating sleep mode
- Energy-saving IT, e.g. through optimized algorithms or **energy-saving** hardware
- Selecting effects and **web fonts** in a way that consumes as little energy and transfers as little data as possible
 - Selecting energy-efficient fonts; pre-installed fonts such as Arial, TNR; ink-saving fonts; tools such as Font Subsetter can be used to cut out unneeded characters
 - Reduction of white space and introduction of **dark mode**

Minimisation of data transmission

Data transmission combines methods for passing on information from an information source (transmitter) to an information sink (receiver). This can be transported by electrical, optical signals or electromagnetic waves⁹. The transmission of data has an impact on our environment, for instance through land use and water consumption of data centers. For this reason, the minimal use of data transmission is a further means of achieving sustainability in IT (software). Possible action points for the guiding principle of minimal data transmission are listed below:

- If data is to be transmitted in streaming mode (i.e. in real time), then in a lower **resolution**
- Paying attention to **clean code**:
 - Reducing or minimizing complex scripts (minimizing removes additional characters),
 - Avoiding unnecessary plugins,
 - Avoiding redundancy

⁸ see Haufe, 2021.

⁹ cf. data transmission, n.d.

- Writing efficient queries (requests to a database),
- Ensuring that the used frameworks and libraries respect the reduction of media content (e.g. images and videos)
- Reducing **third-party code**:
 - Using "preconnect" or "dns prefetch" resource hints to establish early connections to third-party origins and improving charging performance
- Using current, data-reduced **image formats**
- Avoiding **dynamic content** (e.g. automatically changing designs, automatically playable videos, automatic data transfer, etc.)
- Configuring **default settings** so that as little data as possible is transferred
- Avoiding **tracking**, i.e. user data should not be transferred (to other) providers
- Avoiding **redirects** to other services (e.g. payment services) for avoiding unnecessary redirects and reducing loading time
- Avoiding **advertising** or advertising scripts
- Avoiding **cookies**
- Avoiding automatic **playback** of content e.g. video auto-play
- Enabling users to **control the data**, e.g. by making the settings for data transmission easily accessible
- Avoiding **sensory overload**, e.g. through static content, slow content changes, infrequent content updates
- Avoiding **confusing user experience** (UX design) with the help of e.g. Cumulative Layout Shift measurement
- Using **lazy loading** by loading images and other media content only when they appear in the user's visible area
- Minimizing **server requests** by caching, lazy loading, reducing HTTP requests, using HTTP/2 protocol (multiplexing allows multiple requests in a single connection path)

Minimisation of data storage

Data storage is the process of storing data in electromagnetic or optical form. This can be done on a storage disk, on the device itself or in the cloud¹⁰. Data storage has an impact on the environment: When data is stored more minimalistically, land, CO2 and water are consumed in the data centers operating the clouds. For this reason, the minimisation of data storage is another key to achieving sustainability in IT (software). Possible action points for this guiding principle are listed below:

- Ensuring data recoverability, e.g. through regular archiving of data
- Avoiding duplicates
- Regular deletion of unnecessary files, content, etc.
- Using less data through data compression:
 - Using tools such as SVGO, TinyPNG and others for significantly compressing **images** such as JPGs, SVGs, PNGs; combining icons in an SVG sprite; compression of HTML, Javascript and CSS source codes
 - Reducing the **resolution** of videos and images, set explicit width and height specifications for images
 - Using the most efficient **file format** for images/graphics, e.g. WebP instead of JPG for images and SVG instead of PNG for icons

¹⁰ cf. Hoogenraad, 2023.

- Reducing the **file size** of videos by compressing them, e.g with the software "HandBrake"
- Designing content in a way that the **computing power** can be adapted to the hardware
- Efficient storage
- Ensuring **platform independence** and portability of the software: developing the software so that it can be executed on different hardware and in different operating systems
- Allowing easy deletion of data
- Offering **deletion** of unused data
- Using **AMP technology** (Accelerated Mobile Pages) for speeding up the loading of apps on mobile devices

Health and accessibility

Health and accessibility of IT in terms of sustainability can be defined as follows. Health is about designing IT in a way that does not cause **physical and mental harm to health**. Ideally, technology is designed in a way that it counteracts unhealthy usage patterns and actively supports users in promoting a healthy lifestyle¹¹ e.g. by **avoiding suggestive notifications**. Accessibility refers to how easy the IT is accessible and useable. High accessibility means that access to data and software is network-based and **inexpensive** or reasonably priced. In addition, the diverse population should be taken into account e.g. through **accessibility**, which can be expressed in an audio function of websites for the deaf or simple language for people with disabilities.¹² The following are possible action points for this guiding principle:

- Avoidance of "**dark patterns**", such as endless feeds, suggestive notifications, rankings or competitions
- No hidden costs
- Promoting comprehensible **settings** and their effects
- Enabling **feedback**
- Protection against manipulation and failures through e.g. **distributed storage**
- Ensuring **data protection**, e.g. through the option of deleting the stored data
- Integrating **night mode** or setting a **timer** to prevent using the app before going to bed
- Reducing stress
 - e.g. through fewer to no **notifications**
 - implementing **break regulations**, e.g. through automated reminders to take breaks or short movement clips
- Consideration of **linguistic diversity**
- Prioritizing **accessibility**: the software should be functional on a variety of devices and platforms, including technologies for people with disabilities, which minimizes user frustration and meets ethical standards

¹¹ & ¹² Grosch et al., 2023.